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Promoting value chain innovations in the emerging “Connected Car” industry: ICCar approach

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Abstract

High-tech small and very small enterprises, like start-ups or spin-offs, are well-known means to bring innovations to the market in the ICT sector. The emerging “connected car” industry offers huge opportunities, but also risks challenges, in creating and developing ICT-based technologies for the automotive sector, as well as new business models beyond the traditional “vehicle manufacturing” industry. This change towards a fully connected mobility involves not only ICT and automotive companies, but also infrastructure builders and operators, transport service providers and the financial sector. This paper summarizes and discusses the approach adopted in the “Impact Connected Car” project, which supports creative and innovative SMEs working in the Connected Car domain, through equity free funding and a smartization and acceleration programme. It also describes the “open space” created by the project, where start-ups and large companies can meet, fostering cross-sectoral fertilisation and new value chain innovations.

Keywords: Connected car, Cascade funding, Smartization programme

Introduction

ICT vs Automotive industry strategy to address innovation

There are remarkable differences between Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the Automotive Sector on how innovation process is addressed. On the one hand, the ICT is characterized by innovative and disruptive solutions that generate emerging ecosystems [1]; with shorter time-to-market and applying novel funding mechanisms (such as business angels, venture capital and funding rounds, and incubators and accelerators, to name of few). This has made possible that small high-tech enterprises have become large global corporates in a very short period of time.

On the other hand, the automotive sector is a mature, capital-intensive and asset-based industry [2]; comprising large and longstanding companies; with product development times larger; high quality and safety requirements and a well established supply and value chains. In this context, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) and TIER 1 suppliers have been the leading companies in driving innovation within the automotive sector. Traditionally innovation in this industry is closed [3], with high focus on IP rights and organized according to a stage-gate process [4].

The emergence of the “Connected Car” industry

All sectors of the economy are to a greater or lesser extent affected by the digitalization. The sector is not an exception to this and the traditional value chain is rapidly changing (Figure 1, [5]), challenged by new market entrants [6]. Digitalization affects the manufacturing process but also the vehicle itself, with the introduction of advanced driving assistance & infotainment systems, among others.

Figure 1. The emerging mobility ecosystem

Therefore, new business models based on ICT technologies are making its way into the mobility ecosystem, in interaction with changes in society as a whole. For instance, it is expected that up to 36% of citizens in 2025 will be using the sharing economy instead of owning a car [7]. This shift will be even greater with the forthcoming autonomous cars.

Cross-sectoral hybridisation

Due to all the above, a combination of both ICT and automotive innovation approaches is needed. Currently, there is a list of auto-supported incubators and accelerators that are boosting innovation and working with startups from connected mobility to autonomous vehicles and smart city solutions.

Accelerator programs involving high-tech SMEs, which bring novel ideas of interest for the automotive sector, are promoted by car-makers such as the PSA Group 4 Developers [8], a chance to be the creator of the future applications for connected vehicles. Also, SEAT Connector [9] in automotive, mobility and logistic sectors. Daimler has three different initiatives: Startup Autobahn [10], Startup Autobahn Singapore [11] and Lab 1986 [12]. Moreover, Jaguar Land Rover has created Jaguar Land Rover Innovation Labs [13] and BMW supports startups with an innovative technology through Start Garage [14]. Ford has created two Accelerators, one in US, Techstars Mobility [15] and the other one, The Automotive Industry Development Centre (AIDC), established in South Africa with

local governments and OEMs. General Motors [16] directly invests in growth-stage startups through GM Ventures. DRIVE Automotive Technology Incubator [17] is an Israel-based startup mobility accelerator founded by Mayer Cars and Trucks Ltd. It is selecting startups working on areas including sensors and computer vision. Volkswagen hosted at the Transparent Factory its 1st innovative startup mobility programme in 2017 [18]. TAMO [19] is Tata Motors’ incubating center of innovation towards new technologies, business models and partnerships in order to define future mobility solutions. Since 2012, Toyota has created the Toyota Innovation Hub (TIH) [20] and Honda has created the programme Honda Xcelerator [21] to give access to Xcelerator vehicles and vehicle data to develop, test and refine the prototypes.

In addition, the development of new mobility products and services will require the involvement of infrastructure builders and operators and service providers as well, among others. One successful example is the Israeli start-up Argus, which provides solutions to protect connected cars against cyber-attacks. Continental AG has recently announced that they have acquire Argus to be part of its subsidiary Elektrobit [22].

Another successful example of this novel combination is car-sharing. Several OEMs are already promoting car-sharing services, such as PSA Group with Emov, Daimler AG with Car2Go, BMW with DriveNow, Renault with Zity or Ford with GoDrive.

Impact Connected Car approach

Methodology

In this evolving context that the automotive industry is facing, Impact Connected Car (ICCar) project aims at applying a methodology to discover and accelerate start-ups with innovative ideas for the emerging sector linked to the Connected Car. To achieve this goal, the project implements a cascade funding model, an instrument that the European Commission is prioritizing in order to boost emerging companies (e.g. Future Internet Core Platform [11]). ICCar is the first cascade funding project focused exclusively on the Connected Car ecosystem, with the participation of large corporations (PSA Group, Ferrovial, Fiware Foundation), RTOs, associations and clusters (CTAG, Mov’eo, INSERO, Autoklastr, FIA, LPNT and PARP), business acceleration experts (FundingBox, ISDI), among other project partners. The following subsections describe the phases of the “funneling” process adopted in the project to select and support the most promising enterprises.

Connected car open space

As initial step to leverage this hybridation, an Open Space was created. This Open Space is virtual and physical network of Connected Car Hubs (C-Car Hubs). The purpose of these C-Car Hubs is to foster synergies among the clusters and their members, in order to speed up interaction, common understandings and interests, in the emerging Connected Car industry. CTAG, as leader of the C-Car Hubs, in collaboration with other EU clusters, is working with leading industries in addressing the

multi-sectoral challenge: automotive, mobility, ICT, electronics, infrastructure, building, and consumer and business services.

Disruptors discovery

To discover those innovative connected car start-ups, Open Calls has been planned to seek innovative solutions addressed to six specific verticals related to connected car. As it is described in Table 1, the projects shall support the driver assistance, vehicle or mobility management, functions involving the entertainment or driver’s comfort and ability, or safety and security aspects.

DRIVER ASSISTANCE	VEHICLE MANAGEMENT	MOBILITY MANAGEMENT
Functions involving partially or fully automatic driving.	Functions that aid the driver in reducing operating costs and improving ease of use.	Functions that allow the driver to reach a destination quickly, safely, and in a cost-efficient manner.
INFOTAINMENT	WELL-BEING	SAFETY & SECURITY
Functions involving the entertainment of the driver and passengers.	Functions involving the driver’s comfort and ability and fitness to drive.	Functions that warn the driver of external hazards and internal responses of the vehicle to hazards.

Table 1 Technological verticals

Innovative solutions might solve specific issues related to each of the six verticals:

- **Driver assistance:**
 - Operational assistance or autopilot in heavy traffic, in parking or on highways.
 - 3D Cloud Based Navigation.
 - Cruise control.
 - Self-driving.
 - Speed/distance advice.
- **Vehicle management:**
 - Vehicle conditions and service reminders.
 - Remote operation and SW updated.
 - Transfer of usage data.
 - Driver Performance Analytics.
 - Electronic tolling and road usage.
 - Car sharing/Car-pooling Systems, mainly for EV and PHEV use-cases
 - Vehicle-to-Grid capabilities.
 - Customer profiling. Promotions.
 - For fleets: for loaf identification and characterization, for EV and PHEV use-cases.

- For maintenance of fleets: correspondence of the work order to the tools and protection equipment loaded into the vehicle.
- Vehicle Communication (V2X).

- **Mobility management:**
 - Current traffic info (floating car data/ITS).
 - Maps/street view.
 - Journey Planner.
 - Parking lot or garage assistance.
 - Services to Electric Vehicles: Schedule charging slot, near charging stations and prices, estimate driving range/battery, home charging.
 - Optimised Fuel consumption/Eco driving.
 - Hazardous climatic conditions warning and driving tips.
 - Vehicle as part of the IoT.

- **Infotainment:**
 - Smartphone interface, mainly for EV and PHEV use-cases
 - WLAN hot spot.
 - Internet services.
 - Social media and networking
 - Personal info management.
 - Mobile office.
 - Advertisement and Points of Interest, Trip info.
 - Hotel/restaurant easy booking.
 - In-vehicle secure open access service platform.

- **Well-being:**
 - Fatigue detection.
 - Alco-lock.
 - Seat Adjustment.
 - Services/functions to active ageing or to disable persons.
 - Driver distraction alert.
 - Driver health monitoring.

- **Safety and security:**
 - Collision avoidance (blind spot monitoring), intersection pilot, lane assistant, autonomous braking, traffic sign violation warning.
 - Hazards warning.
 - Emergency call (eCall).
 - Protection of Vulnerable Road Users.
 - Cybersecurity;
 - Stolen Vehicle Tracking and Recovery.

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- Roadside assistance.
- Pavement Conditions measurement.

Smartization programme

To accelerate those innovative connected car start-ups, the selected projects were invited to join an innovative smartization programme, whose three main stages are:

- Stage 1. “Disruptive Boot Camp” to allow interactions between disruptive start-ups and SMEs and large enterprise to select the most promising ideas.
- Stage 2. “Ignition Plan”, focused on assessing the technical feasibility and market potential as well as defining a plan to execute it.
- Stage 3. The best performance projects access to the “Product Development”, focused on supporting the development and validation of new services, products and/or processes at market level.

The main drivers of the three stages are “Boot Camps”, “Coaching services” and “Transversal services” which include marketing, legal and talent recruitment services.

In particular, multidisciplinary coaching services, organised as a totally customised service, where high level coaches and top professionals are specifically selected to fit start-ups and SMEs’ needs: business (day-by-day business decisions), technical (maximising the absorption of technical capabilities), corporate (to supervise the project evolution and facilitate the coordination towards new industrial value chains) and funding (to help start-ups and SMEs to get additional funds).

Value Chain links generation & Sustainability

The final phase is focused on consolidating a long term relationship between the most promising connected car start-ups SMEs supported in the project and large companies in the targeted sectors.

Figure 2 Phases of the Impact Connected Car approach

Results achieved

A total of 218 applications have been submitted to the First Open Call, whose deadline was on January the 10th, 2018. Solutions addressed to Mobility and Vehicle management are at the top of the

technological interest showed by applicants. Solutions addressed to Safety, Driver assistance or Well-being represents each one around the 10% of the total. However, solutions to enhance the Infotainment at connected car represent only the 7% of the total solutions submitted.

Regarding the origin of the applications, Spain leads the ranking with the 23% of them, followed by Poland (12%). The percentage of applicants from Italy, France and Portugal are over 10%. United Kingdom, Germany and Czech Republic are also present, with 4% of the applications.

Figure 3 Technological and geographical interest in emerging connected car

Once the evaluation process finished, a total of 25 start-ups were selected to participate in the 1st stage of the smartization programme (Figure 2). Although most of them (88%) have a maturity in the market less than three years, 76% have already established links with mobility stakeholders: OEM or TIER, IT or telecommunication enterprises, insurance enterprises, infrastructure enterprises or others, such as policy makers, RTO or wholesalers.

In particular, seven start-ups and SMEs have already established collaboration with one stakeholder and nine with two different stakeholders. On the other hand, only three start-ups and SMEs have links with three different stakeholders. The following Figure 4 shows the overall collaborations that start-ups and SMEs have already established with the different mobility stakeholders.

Figure 4 Collaborations established with mobility stakeholders

Regarding the entrepreneurship expertise of teams, it is known that the 72% of the 25 start-ups and

SMEs have participated in previous acceleration initiatives or programmes. Ten teams (40%) have participated in several of them.

Figure 5 Entrepreneurship expertise of teams

The 25 projects selected from the first Open Call to go through the smartization program started with the Disruptive Boot Camp, the first program stage, that was held in CTAG (Spain) during 3 days. In the Boot Camp, the start-ups took part in different activities such as speed pitching and speed meeting sessions, networking, corporates talk and even a visit to the facilities of the Technology Centre.

The last day of the Disruptive Boot Camp, the jury attended the start-ups pitches and decided which were the best to go to the Ignition Plan, the second stage of the ICCar program.

The 15 start-ups and SMEs selected were:

- **Bohr Technology** (Poland): A traffic simulation & route planning system powered by AI & Quantum Computing.
- **CardioID Technologies** (Portugal): Enabling safer drivers and vehicles through a technology that is able to biometrically identify the driver and produce fatigue and drowsiness alerts.
- **Carfit** (France): AI based technology that reads the vibration of the vehicle to make the car maintenance easier and mobility safer.
- **Carricare b.v. (Chargetrip)** (The Netherlands): Development of predictive deep learning models for fleet managers and energy operators around the world.
- **Eccocar Sharing S.L.** (Spain): Car Sharing solution that optimizes and digitalizes the use of the existing fleets.
- **Homyhub S.L.** (Spain): Universal plug and play solution for garage openers that turns the smartphone into a Smart Garage Remote enabling users to control, monitor and manage access to the garage, anywhere at anytime.
- **Motor Ai** (Germany): A device that enables digital services in vehicles by collecting data of parked and driving vehicles.
- **Parkbob GmbH** (Viena): Parkbob enables a seamless last mile experience by delivering context-aware parking rules & restrictions as well as real-time on-street parkability.
- **Situm Technologies S.L.** (Spain): indoor positioning provider that enables corporations developing new location-based services.

- **Spark Horizon** (Switzerland): Universal charging solution. Spark Horizon conceive, install and operate the 1st European network of free charging stations for electric vehicles, sponsored through AI based advertising.
- **Traffic Network Solutions S.L.** (Spain): Using connected floating car data for optimizing mobility in junctions, roundabouts, work zones...
- **Worldsensing S.L.** (Spain): Platform to provide Operational Intelligence to cities through a plug and play approach which creates a customized solution to solve problems such as traffic or public space safety.
- **Xapix Software GmbH** (Germany): Helping enterprises to drive sales and partner engagement by creating easy-to-integrate digital services with their legacy data
- **Ximantis AB** (Sweden): The project aims to forecast and anticipate, exact traffic congestion hot spots, before they have a chance to form.
- **Y.Share S.r.l.** (Italy): The only patented off the shelf technology to share the car, optimize its usage and turn it into a profit machine.

Conclusions

Although there is still a gap between ICT and automotive sectors to be filled, there are already successful examples of the hybridation of innovation strategies. Impact Connected Car aims to strengthen this effort and become a best-practice example of supporting ICT-based SMEs working in the Connected Car domain.

Among the six verticals considered in ICCar (which are presented in the connected car roadmap of the automotive industry), the mobility and vehicle management challenges are the most appealing for applicants. Connected Car start-ups and SMEs have the potential to disrupt the mobility and/or automotive industry to solve this gap. However, access to OEMs or suppliers still remains limited, though most of them have established collaborations and alliances with indirect stakeholders such IT, telecommunications or insurance providers.

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